

Ethnobotanical survey on threatened medicinal plants in Togo

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Abstract

Local communities heavily rely on the use of plants for disease treatment, notwithstanding modern medicine's progress. However, climate change and anthropic actions exacerbate threat to these medicinal plant's survival. This study aims to list Threatened Medicinal Plants (TMP) in the Guinean Zone of Togo and to access community's traditional knowledge about them. For this purpose, 31 localities were investigated and ethno-medicinal data was collected through semi-structured methods, including individual interviews and focus groups. A total, of 124 TMP were recorded, belonging to 118 genera and 47 families. The top five plant taxa were *Khaya senegalensis* (49.4%), *Sarcocephalus latifolius* (35.5%), *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* (26.1%), *Flueggea virosa* (19.3%) and *Caesalpinia bonduc* (19.0%). The plant parts and mode of preparation most used were respectively leaves (64.8%) and decoction (76.6%). The high Informant Consensus Factor (IFC) (0.79) calculated shows strong agreement on TMP usage according to the disease categories identified. TMP such as *K. grandifoliola*, *K. senegalensis*, *A. africana*, *G. afzelii*, *V. paradoxa*, *P. erinaceus* and *M. excelsa* are vulnerable worldwide according to IUCN criteria. Safeguarding these TMP through their domestication and culture will help to safeguarding TMP and the traditional knowledge about them.

Keywords: Threatened medicinal plant, ethnobotany, conservation, Togo

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INTRODUCTION

Plant genetic resources provide a multitude services for all human-being across the world (Thiombiano *et al.*, 2022). They are still used in numerous fields, and their medicinal use is highly valued (Sofowora, 2010; Chukwuma *et al.*, 2015). Despite the progress of modern medicine (Motto *et al.*, 2021), plant drugs are gaining in popularity among populations (Gadikou *et al.*, 2022), especially in these post Covid-19 times (Haidara *et al.*, 2020), because plant drugs are considered to be less toxic and milder than pharmaceutical product (Briki, 2019; Delhami *et al.*, 2022). As result, 70–95% African people use plants for the treatment of primary symptoms. The plants knowledge (Atakpama *et al.*, 2021), the trust and the medicinal efficacy of plant recipes (Kpoyizoun *et al.*, 2019), and the populations impoverishment (Ouro-Djeri *et al.*, 2022) explain this high increase in plant use (Agbodan, 2023). These reasons have increased anthropic action on medicinal resources, leading to the scarcity of some medicinal phylogenetic resources (Ouro-Djeri *et al.*, 2022). In addition, climate change (Elith *et al.*, 2011; Cain and Douzet, 2022) combined with ecosystem fragility (Adjossou *et al.*, 2022) hampers the chances of survival and perpetuation of medicinal plant species, which are a cultural legacy for various populations (Salako *et al.*, 2021; Favi *et al.*, 2022; Xu *et al.*, 2022). Plants that were once highly prized for treating diseases are seeing their habitat reduced and threatened (Gadikou *et al.*, 2022). There is a need to survey scarce and threatened medicinal plants and their related local knowledge for their conservation to next generations. This study contributes to the conservation of threatened medicinal plants (TMP) with their local knowledge. To

the best author's knowledge, the available information on TMP in the Guinean zone is far from exhaustive. Although previous ethnobotanical surveys of medicinal plants have been conducted in the study area (Agody, 2007; Gnondoli *et al.*, 2015; Holaly *et al.*, 2015; Kpodar *et al.*, 2015; Agbodeka *et al.*, 2016; Kpodar *et al.*, 2016; Agbodeka *et al.*, 2017; Gbekley *et al.*, 2017; Effoe *et al.*, 2020; Atakpama *et al.*, 2021; Gadikou *et al.*, 2022; Ouro-Djeri *et al.*, 2022), few investigations have focused on TMP. Consequently, this work would provide a useful update to a database for the preservation and promotion of ancestral TMP knowledge. Knowledge about diversity and local knowledge of TMP will allow for giving a priority on their conservation. This study aims to (i) list threatened medicinal plants in the Guinean zone of Togo, and (ii) inventory the medicinal uses of these TMP.

MATERIAL ET METHODS

Study area

The choice of the Guinean zone is based on its abundant plant diversity and the pressures from agricultural and urban expansion on the local ecosystem. The study area can be divided into three ecological zones (Ern, 1979). The plains zone situated in the northeast is characterized by savannas interwoven with dry forests dominated by *Anogeissus leiocarpus*. These savannas exhibit diverse flora, with Combretaceae and Andropogonae being the prominent species. Amid these savannas, are pockets of semi-deciduous forests and gallery forests featuring primary species like *Cynometra megalophylla*, *Parinari congensis*, and *Pterocarpus santalinoides*. The mountainous zone (ecological zone IV) in the northwest consists of semi-deciduous humid forests (Akpagana,

1989). Species found here include *Hidalgardia barberi*, *Khaya grandifoliola*, *Milicia excelsa*, *Morus mesozygia*, *Parkia filicoidea*, *Musanga cecropioides*, *Triplochiton scleroxylon*, and *Pterocarpus midbraedii*. These forests are interspersed with savannas containing species such as *Lophira lanceolata*, *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, *Hymenocardia acida*, *Crossopteryx febrifuga*, *Faurea speciosa*, and *Vitex doniana*. This region also harbors 110 locally threatened species and 16 globally vulnerable species, as per the IUCN criteria, highlighting its ecological significance (Adjossou, 2009).

The coastal plain (ecological zone V) to the south showcases a diverse landscape including croplands, fallow areas, thickets, bushes, and grassy savannas, along with sacred and community forests (Folega *et al.*, 2023). Mangroves, flooded meadows, and savannas also thrive

in the extreme southeast. This study holds particular importance in mitigating human-induced impacts on these ecosystems, reinforcing the conservation of threatened medicinal plants (TMP), promoting sustainable management practices, and safeguarding the valuable indigenous knowledge pertaining to TMP.

Ethnobotanical survey and data collection

The localities to be investigated were chosen on a stratified sampling basis (Akpavi *et al.*, 2007). Strata selected were ecological zones (Ern, 1979) and the spread of ethnocultural groups (Gayibor, 1997) (Figure 1). An explorative survey was carried out to evaluate the understanding of the questionnaire and to determine the size of sample to be surveyed.

Figure 1: Prospecting points

The sample was determined by Dagnelie's formula (Dagnelie, 1998) $N = \frac{U_{1-\alpha/2}^2 \times p(1-p)}{d^2}$, where N is the sample size to be determined; p is the proportion (relative frequency) of respondents with knowledge about TMP; $U_{1-\alpha/2}$ is the standard value of confidence level (interval); and d is the margin of error set at 5% for this study. This formula provides a theoretical sample of person to be surveyed. It has been used by several authors to determine the size of the surveyed sampling (Agbodan et al., 2020; Awo et al., 2020; Bi et al., 2020). Thus, several householders were surveyed in each locality with the goal to obtain a maximum and redundancy in information on TMP and their related local knowledge. Given the specificity of the information searched, adults (30-60 years) and older people (> 60 years) were favored. In each locality, resource people were selected with the help of local leaders. After explanation of the objectives, the local leaders and agricultural managers assembled people who fulfilled the criteria of the investigation. This approach has the advantage to build a mutual climate of trust and enables the collection of reliable and accurate information on a highly sensitive topic of medicinal plant. The ethics code was carefully followed, and an oral agreement "agreeing to be interviewed" from the community authorities and each interviewee, in accordance with the principles of the ethics ISE code was received. So, 352 interviewees from 31 localities and 10 cultural groups were surveyed from April to September 2022 throughout the study area. The Ewe, Adja, and Kabyè communities were investigated more, because of their widespread geographic distribution (Gayibor, 1997). Data were collected through semi structured individual and focus group (Akpavi et al., 2013). The questions are focused on medicinal plants, which were used in the past but no longer exists in the area, local knowledge related to these medicinal plants, plant organs, preparation, administration method, and diseases treated.

Classification of medicinal uses

The various diseases and symptoms were grouped into categories defined by the International Classification of Primary Care, Second Edition (Jamouille et al., 2000). This classification has been used in several research related to medicinal plants (Gumisiriza et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2019; Miara et al., 2019; Anywar et al., 2020). These are general and unspecified diseases (A), blood and

immunological system diseases (B), digestive system diseases (D), cardiovascular diseases (K), osteoarticular diseases (L), neurological diseases (N), psychological diseases (P), pregnancy and childbirth diseases (W), respiratory diseases (R), skin diseases (S), endocrine metabolism diseases (T), female genital system diseases (X), and male genital system diseases (Y).

Statut IUCN et statut local des TMP

The TMP identified was compared to the IUCN Red List (List, 2015) and local red lists (Radji, 2008; Adjossou, 2009; Atsri et al., 2018). The red list allows us to know the risk of extinction of species, and to monitor changes in the status of species (Kaky & Gilbert, 2019). The classes defined are Extinct (EX), Extinct in the Wild (EW), Critically Endangered (CR), Endangered (EN), Vulnerable (VU), Near Threatened (NT), and Least Concern (LC). According to the latest categorization, species considered threatened include those that are critically endangered, endangered and vulnerable. The R software, via rredlist package, was used to establish the status of TMP identified (Whitney, 2022).

Data Analysis

The collected data are inputted and encoded in the Excel for analysis. The Ethnobotany package of Rstudio software was used to generate basic quantitative indices in ethnobotany (Table 1). These are the reported uses (UR), the index of cultural importance (IC), and the consensus factor index (CFI).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondents' profile

The largest numbers of respondents were native people (84.4%), given the specific nature of the topic (Table 2). The sex ratio was 0.87, indicating a nearly equal distribution of interviewees by gender. Adults and elderly people (over 35 years old) were the most investigated age groups. The number of dependents (children) was low (0-5) in 42.0% of households investigated. The respondents were occasional users (77.0%), traditional practitioners (19.6%), and resellers (3.4%), and 40.1% of these categories were illiterate. The results indicate that a low level of education does not hamper the acquisition

Table 1: Indices used to describe threatened medicinal plant knowledge

Calculated index	Method	Interpretation
Reported uses (RU) $RU = \sum_{u=1}^{u_{NC}} \sum_{i=1}^{i_N} UR_{ui}$	Calculates the total uses for the species by all informants (from i_1 to i_N) within each use-category for that species (i)	Calculates the cultural importance index (CI) for each TMP among ethnocultural group prospected (Prance et al., 1987).
Consensus Factor Index (CFI) $CFI = (Nur - Nt) / (Nur - 1)$	Nur, the number of times a disease category was mentioned; and Nt, the number of PMTs used in the treatment of that disease category	This index makes it possible to evaluate the degree of homogeneity of the information received from the respondents (Tardío & Pardo-de-Santayana, 2008).
Cultural Importance Index (CI) $IC = Na / NT$	Na, number of people who cited the medicinal plant for a given disease divided by NT, the number of people who cited the plant	Nur, the number of times a disease category was mentioned; and Nt, the number of PMTs used in the treatment of that disease category (Reyes-García et al., 2019).

of medicinal plant practices. Our results support those of Kpodar *et al.*, (2015, 2016) in Togo. The number of threatened medicinal plants did not vary significantly according to respondent age, education level or household size. However, a significant difference at the 5% threshold was observed for the variables gender, type of respondent and distance of the locality from the nearest hospital (Table 1). Results are similar to those of work of Kébenzikato *et al.*, (2015) in Togo, on the influence of socio-economic parameters on local knowledge about *Adansonia digitata*.

Medicinal plant diversity

Semi-structured interview helped to identify 124 TMP belonging to 118 genera and 47 families (Table 3). This rich diversity of TMP indicates a good knowledge of medicinal plants that are becoming rare, disappearing, or difficult to access (Gaur and Sharma, 2011), an area rich in highly anthropized ecosystems (Adjossou, 2009; Koda *et al.*, 2019), a poor economic status of the residents, and an attachment to plants for the diseases treatment (Ouro-Djeri *et al.*, 2022). Fabaceae (21 species), Euphorbiaceae (12 species), Apocynaceae (7 species), Compositae (5 species), and Rutaceae (5 species) are the most abundant botanical families identified (Figure 2). More than half-botanical families are represented by one or two species. The most frequently cited TMP are *Khaya senegalensis* (49.4%), *Sarcocephalus latifolius* (35.5%), *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* (26.1%), *Flueggea virosa* (19.3%), *Caesalpinia bonduc* (19.0%), *Bridelia ferruginea* (16.19%), *Acanthospermum hispidum* (15.63%), *Uvaria chamae* (14.8%), *Morinda lucida* (13.7%), and

Alstonia boonei (12.2%). Our results reinforce those of Gadikou *et al.*, (2022) working on vulnerable medicinal plants in the maritime region of Togo. Seventy-eight (78) species are similar between the two studies. Seven (07) TMP are involved in the treatment of more than five (05) diseases. These plants, qualified as versatile, offer a wide range of recipes for the treatment of diseases. It is about *A. hispidum*, *A. floribunda*, *C. bonduc*, *Jatropha curcas*, *K. senegalensis*, *M. lucida*, and *Vitex doniana*. According to Schulz *et al.*, (2001), for a given therapeutic indication, the traditherapist can cite several plants to hide the one containing the active ingredient. Sanon *et al.* (2003) showed significant inhibitory activity of *A. hispidum* (IC₅₀ = 5.02 µg/mL) on *Plasmodium falciparum* isolates from children between 4 and 10 years old in Burkina Faso. In addition, Ram *et al.* (Ram *et al.*, 2004) proved the efficacy of *A. hispidum* (5000 µg/mL) against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Candida albicans*. These results can explain the folk utilization of *A. hispidum* in malaria and sinusitis treatment.

Alchornea floribunda inhibit *Bacillus cereus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Escherichia coli*, which are responsible of gastrointestinal disease, and, *Klebsiella pneumonia* and *Moraxella catarrhalis*, responsible of respiratory disease (Noundou *et al.*, 2014). These results confirm the traditional use of *A. floribunda* for respiratory and gastrointestinal (diarrhea) disease collected. Afolabi and Abejide (2020) reported in vitro activity of *Alstonia bonei* leaf extract against *P. falciparum*. The biological properties presented by plant extracts give credit to their indigenous uses. However, twelve plants have not been studied to show the safety and toxicity of TMP. It's

Table 2: TMP collected according to respondents' profile

Caterory	Variable (Number)	Mean ± SD	Statistical analyses
Sex	Woman (163)	8.75 ± 4.28 a	Pr (> F) = 0.000593
	Man (189)	7.29 ± 3.67 b	
Type of respondent	Herbalist (69)	8.64 ± 4.29 a	Pr (> F) = 7.97e-10
	Resellers (12)	14.7 ± 0.87 b	
	Occasional user (271)	7.49 ± 3.74 a	
Respondant age	20 - 30 (54)	7.2 ± 3.19 a	Pr (> F) = 0.0283
	31 - 40 (88)	7.48 ± 3.63 a	
	41 - 50 (86)	8.69 ± 4.22 a	
	51 - 60 (56)	9.11 ± 4.86 a	
	61 - 70 (44)	7.14 ± 4.2 a	
	sup 71 (24)	7.75 ± 3.15 a	
Education level	Illiterate (141)	8.04 ± 3.79 a	Pr (> F) = 0.44
	College (73)	8.38 ± 4.05 a	
	High school (15)	8 ± 4.14 a	
	Primary (120)	7.71 ± 4.29 a	
	University (3)	4.33 ± 2.31 a	
Household size	0 - 5 (148)	8.09 ± 4.22 a	Pr (> F) = 0.112
	6 - 10 (170)	7.76 ± 3.72 a	
	11 - 15 (23)	9.48 ± 5.15 a	
	16 - 20 (11)	6.18 ± 1.99 a	
Distance from hospital	< 5 km (200)	8.4 ± 4.28 a	Pr (> F) = 0.00000589
	10 à 15 km (21)	10.9 ± 5.95 b	
	5 à 10 km (131)	6.84 ± 2.71 c	

about *A. hispidum*, *A. floribunda*, *A. albida*, *C. bonduc*, *C. viscosa*, *D. mespiliformis*, *J. curcas*, *L. taraxacifolia*, *M. lucida*, *N. latifolia*, *P. foetida*, and *X. aethiopica*.

Launaea taraxacifolia has antimalarial, antiviral against the measles virus, antiarthritic, anti-inflammatory and bactericidal activities (Bello et al., 2018; Owolabi et al., 2020). *Milicia excelsa* is anticonvulsant, anti-amnesic, antipsychotic, antihypoxic activities (Adebayo et al., 2019; Akinpelu et al., 2020). These pharmacological properties can explain traditional uses in malaria and female sterility treatment.

Securidaca longipedunculata has antiparasitic, antibacterial, antifungal, antiplasmodial, anti-inflammatory, anticonvulsant, histopathologic activities (Alitonou et al., 2012; Mongalo et al., 2015). These properties can explain traditional uses against snakebite, sinusitis and head wounds. However, there is a need to study the toxicity of these plants to ensure safe and effective use in populations.

IUCN Statut vs. local Statut of TMP

Different conservation statuses of TMP were determined (Figure 3). These include vulnerable species (VU) with 2.21% and are represented by species such as *K. grandifoliola*, *K. senegalensis*, *A. africana*, *G. afzelii*, and *V. paradoxa*. Threatened species (EN) with 0.74% are represented by *P. erinaceus*, while *M. excelsa* is the representative of the near-threatened species (NT) with 0.74%. Nearly 87 plant species are not evaluated (NE) by the IUCN. These results corroborate work which reports that, the IUCN Red List, although providing threat levels

at the global level, has limitations because only 5.5% of plant species are assessed (List, 2015; Heywood, 2017). Thus, the threat status of plants varies more at local level than the international level, and several species may be threatened at the local level but not be evaluated at international level. In addition, the level of threat may differ by locality, region, or even continent. Among the 124 TMP identified, twenty-five (25) are classified as vulnerable according to the GBIF-Togo, the national herbarium, and the Togolese flora developed by Radji (2008). It's about *A. africana*, *A. adianthifolia*, *A. floribunda*, *A. nobilis*, *A. vogelii*, *B. aethiopum*, *C. edulis*, *C. pentandra*, *D. senegalensis*, *D. mespiliformis*, *E. angolense*, *G. afzelii*, *G. kola*, *H. floribunda*, *K. anotheca*, *K. grandifoliola*, *K. senegalensis*, *M. altissima*, *M. lutea*, *M. excelsa*, *P. excelsa*, *P. erinaceus*, *P. santalinoides*, *T. scleroxylon* and *V. paradoxa*.

This study is in line with the one conducted by Adjosou (2009) in the forest zone (ecological zone IV) of Togo. Thus, 23 TMP were cited as threatened in the forest present in ecological zone IV of Togo. These are *A. digitata*, *A. africana*, *A. adianthifolia*, *A. floribunda*, *A. nobilis*, *A. vogelii*, *B. aethiopum*, *C. edulis*, *C. pentandra*, *D. senegalense*, *D. mespiliformis*, *G. afzelii*, *G. kola*, *H. floribunda*, *K. senegalensis*, *M. lutea*, *M. excelsa*, *P. excelsa*, *P. erinaceus*, *P. santalinoides*, *T. scleroxylon*, *V. paradoxa* and *X. aethiopica*. In comparison with the red list of Benin (Neuenschwander et al., 2011), twenty-one (21) TMP are classified as vulnerable. This study has the merit of identifying 35 other TMP (not cited in previous work in Togo) which becoming threatened in study area.

Table 3: Species of TMP with information on their families, plants parts and medicinal use, ecological zone, ethnobotanical indices (UR, Ivi, and CI), local names, and IUCN status

TMP/Family	Medicinal use TMP	Plant parts	Preparation method	Ecological zone	UR	Ivi	CI	Local name	Statut IUCN
<i>Acacia dudgeoni</i>	Diarrhea / baby's tummy ache / constipation / snakebite	Bark / leaves / root	Decoction / trituration	I, II	27	0.143	0.081	Kabétumbé/Peu	LC
<i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i>	Abscess / wounds / hematoma / hypertension / jaundice / anemia / headache / scorpion bite / malaria / typhoid fever / sinusitis	Leaves / whole plant	Decoction / maceration / trituration	I, II, III, IV, V	55	0.429	0.164	Lan gbanisoè/Ka	NE
<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	Anemia	Root	Decoction	I, II, III, V	4	0.071	0.012	Adzidotsi/Ew	NE
<i>Afraegle paniculata</i>	Intestinal wound	Root	Food	II, III, V	9	0.071	0.027	Ngoné/Ka	NE
<i>Aframomum melegueta</i>	Abdominal and intestinal wound/vomiting	Fruit / grain	Maceration	III, IV, V	26	0.214	0.078	Colombo/Ka	NE
<i>Afzelia africana</i>	Whooping cough / sexual dysfunction	Root	Decoction	I, II, III, V	7	0.143	0.021	Wéré/Ka	VU
<i>Albizia adianthifolia</i>	Asthma / stomach ache	Leaves	Decoction / maceration	III, IV, V	14	0.143	0.042	Ziwa/Adj	LC
<i>Alchornea cordifolia</i>	Wounds / constipation	Root	Decoction	II, III, IV, V	2	0.071	0.006	Zowou/Ka	LC
<i>Alchornea floribunda</i>	Colic / dysentery / toothache / respiratory problems / urinary problems / ulcers	Leaves / root / stem	Decoction	IV	32	0.214	0.096	Ayraba/Ew	LC

Table 3: Continued

TMP/Family	Medicinal use TMP	Plant parts	Preparation method	Ecological zone	UR	Ivi	CI	Local name	Statut IUCN
<i>Allophylus africanus</i>	Migraine / wounds	Leaves	Maceration / trituration	I, II, III, IV, V	11	0.143	0.033	Assiviaton/ Mi	LC
<i>Aloe buettneri</i>	Stomach ache	Sap	Leaves juice	I, II, IV	3	0.071	0.009	Aloes/Ew	NE
<i>Alstonia boonei</i>	Abdominal wounds / malaria	Bark	Decoction	IV	43	0.143	0.128	Nyamidua/ Ew	LC
<i>Annona muricata</i>	Diabetes / cancer / blood pressure	Leaves / grain	Decoction	I, II, III, IV, V	11	0.214	0.033	Agnigli/Ew	LC
<i>Anogeissus leiocarpa</i>	Sexual dysfunction/ mental disorder/malaria	Bark / leaves	Decoction	I, II, III, IV, V	10	0.143	0.03	Tchininga/Te	LC
<i>Anthocleista dja-lonensis</i>	Cough / hernia / aphrodisiac / intestinal wounds	Leaves / root / stem	Decoction / trituration	I, II	26	0.286	0.078	Gboloba/Ew	LC
<i>Anthocleista nobilis</i>	Headaches / wounds	Bark / root	Decoction / trituration	IV	14	0.143	0.042	Gboloba/ Ew	LC
<i>Anthocleista vogelii</i>	Epilepsy	Root	Decoction	IV	13	0.143	0.039	Gboloba/Ew	LC
<i>Aristolochia albida</i>	Snakebite	Leaves	Maceration	II, III	35	0.071	0.104	Gadagali/Ew	NE
<i>Bidens pilosa</i>	Snakebite	Leaves	Cataplasm	II, IV, V	7	0.071	0.021	Dzany- ipipi/Ew	NE
<i>Blighia sapida</i>	Good shape / guinea worm / athlete's foot	Bark / leaves	Maceration	II, III, IV, V	12	0.143	0.036	Kpizou/Ka	LC
<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>	Smallpox	Root	Maceration	I, III, V	2	0.143	0.006	Avhaxasa/Ew	NE
<i>Borassus aethiopum</i>	Sore throat	Root	Decoction	I, II, III, V	13	0.071	0.039	Agoti/Ew	LC
<i>Bridelia ferruginea</i>	Dysentery / constipation / ulcers / de-worming	Bark / leaves / root	Decoction	I, II, III, IV, V	57	0.214	0.17	Akamati/ Ew	LC
<i>Burkea africana</i>	Epilepsy / toothache	root / stem	Decoction	I, II, III, IV	24	0.143	0.072	Tchingli/Ka	LC
<i>Caesalpinia bonduc</i>	Diuretic / headache / stomach ache / malaria/ wounds/cough/vomiting	Leaves / grain / seed / root	Decoction / piler	III, V	67	0.5	0.2	Adikou/Ew	NE
<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i>	Antiviral	Leaves	Decoction / roasting / trituration	III, V	1	0.071	0.003	Gbatog- bato/Ew	LC
<i>Carissa edulis</i>	Sexual dysfunction	Root / stem	Decoction	II, III, V	9	0.071	0.027	Boetso/Ew	LC
<i>Cassia alata</i>	Dermatosis	Leaves	Decoction / maceration	I, II, III, IV, V	8	0.071	0.024	Madonso- homè/Ew	LC
<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	Dysmenorrhea / tension	Flower / root	Decoction	I, II, III, IV, V	11	0.143	0.033	Flawavig- bé/Ew	NE
<i>Ceiba pentandra</i>	Fracture / wounds	Leaves	Maceration	I, II, III, IV, V	12	0.143	0.036	Komoulé/ Ag	LC
<i>Chenopodium ambrosioides</i>	Dermatosis / edema / chickenpox	Bark/ leaves/stem	Decoction / maceration	III, IV, V	16	0.143	0.048	Emigbe/ Ew	NE
<i>Chrysobalanus icaco</i>	Laxative	Grain	Trituration	V	3	0.071	0.009		NE
<i>Cissus populnea</i>	Edema / wounds	Leaves / root	Decoction / maceration	I, II, III, IV, V	14	0.143	0.042	Mènè/Ka	NE
<i>Clausena anisata</i>	Aphrodisiac / measles	Root / stem	Roasting	II, IV, V	5	0.143	0.015	Idenug- bata/Akp	LC
<i>Cleome viscosa</i>	Fever / hemorrhoid / earache / malaria	Leaves	Decoction	I, II, V	34	0.214	0.101	Pepelugbe/ Ew	NE
<i>Cnestis ferruginea</i>	Snakebite	Root	Decoction / maceration	II, III, IV, V	4	0.071	0.012	Tsoade/Ew	NE
<i>Cola gigantea</i>	Against stuttering / leprosy	Leaves	Decoction	II, III, V	7	0.143	0.021		LC
<i>Cola nitida</i>	Incurable wounds	Leaves	Infusion / maceration / trituration	III, IV	4	0.071	0.012	Coroo/Te	LC

Table 3: Continued

TMP/Family	Medicinal use TMP	Plant parts	Preparation method	Ecological zone	UR	Ivi	CI	Local name	Statut IUCN
<i>Combretum micranthum</i>	Fever	Leaves	Decoction	II, III, IV, V	4	0.071	0.012	Bessikaku/Ew	LC
<i>Conyza aegyptiaca</i>	Eczema	Leaves	Maceration / dew water in the leaves	I, II, III, IV, V	9	0.071	0.027		NE
<i>Costus spectabilis</i>	Malaria	Leaves	Powder	II, III	8	0.071	0.024	Tetegugu/Ew	NE
<i>Crateva adansonii</i>	Icterus / sterility	Leaves	Maceration	I, II, III, IV, V	5	0.143	0.015	Watayizan/Ew	LC
<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Malaria	Root	Maceration	I, II, III, IV, V	7	0.071	0.021	Wissikoyè/Ka	DD
<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i>	Snakebite / measles	Root / stem	Trituration	II, III, V	9	0.143	0.027	Sozossi/Te	LC
<i>Diospyros mespiliiformis</i>	Dermatosis / headaches / stomach aches / female infertility	Bark / leaves / root	Decoction	I, II, III, V	34	0.214	0.101	Tigbado/Te	LC
<i>Entandrophragma angolense</i>	Malaria	Bark	Decoction	IV	3	0.071	0.009		NT
<i>Erythrina senegalensis</i>	Aphrodisiac / dysuria	Root / stem	Decoction	I, II, III, IV, V	22	0.143	0.066	Gbengben tchikoloka/Te	LC
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	Tension	Leaves	Decoction / infusion / maceration	I, II, III, IV, V	13	0.143	0.039	Notsigbe/Ew	NE
<i>Euphorbia poissonii</i>	Constipation	Leaves	Decoction	II, III	7	0.071	0.021	Adikpui/Ew	NE
<i>Flacourtia flavescens</i>	Dermatitis / diarrhea	Leaves	Cataplasm / decoction	III, V	13	0.143	0.039	Dégogo/Ew	NE
<i>Garcinia afzelii</i>	Sexual dysfunction	Root	Decoction	IV	2	0.071	0.006		VU
<i>Garcinia kola</i>	Sexual dysfunction / snakebite / shingles	Fruit / grain / seed	Decoction	IV	15	0.214	0.045	Ahowe/Ew	VU
<i>Gliricidia sepium</i>	Fever / malaria	Leaves	Roasting	I, II, III, IV, V	1	0.071	0.003		NE
<i>Harrisonia abyssinica</i>	Diabetes / wounds	Leaves	Decoction	III, V	12	0.143	0.036	Xedza/Ew	LC
<i>Heliotropium indicum</i>	Dermatitis / hypertension / canker sores / tension	Leaves/flower/fruit/whole plant / stem	Decoction	III, IV, V	31	0.286	0.093	Koklotadoe/Ew	NE
<i>Holarrhena floribunda</i>	Diarrhea / fever / sexual impotence	Bark / leaves / root	Decoction	I, II, III, IV, V	10	0.214	0.03	Sesewu/Ew	LC
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>	Good shape	Root	Decoction / trituration	I, II, III, IV, V	4	0.071	0.012	Bedje/Ew	NE
<i>Jatropha curcas</i>	Diabetes / malaria / wounds / female sterility / tetanus / cough	Leaves/root / sap/stem	Decoction / maceration	I, II, III, IV, V	40	0.429	0.119	Babatihé/Ew	LC
<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i>	sexual asthenia / fever / malaria	Leaves / stem	Decoction	I, II, III, IV, V	13	0.214	0.039	Babatidjin/Ew	LC
<i>Jatropha multifida</i>	Wounds	Leaves	Decoction	I, II, III, IV, V	4	0.071	0.012	Tètwwima/Ew	NE
<i>Kalanchoe crenata</i>	Epilepsy / vomiting	Sap	Decoction / maceration	IV	24	0.214	0.072	Aflatogan/Ew	NE
<i>Khaya anthotheca</i>	Antiseptic	Stem	Decoction	IV	1	0.071	0.003	Mahogen/Ew	VU
<i>Khaya grandifoliola</i>	Anemia / malaria / abdominal pain / malaria	Bark	Trituration	II, IV	29	0.143	0.087	Mahogen/Ew	VU
<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	Anemia / anthelmintic / hemorrhoid / headache / edema / malaria / abdominal and intestinal wounds	Bark / leaves / root	Decoction / maceration / trituration	I, II, III	170	0.429	0.507	Mahogen/Ew	VU

Table 3: Continued

TMP/Family	Medicinal use TMP	Plant parts	Preparation method	Ecological zone	UR	Ivi	CI	Local name	Statut IUCN
<i>Kigelia africana</i>	Abdominal wounds	Bark / leaves	Decoction	II, III, IV, V	26	0.214	0.078	Gnak-pekpe/Ew	LC
<i>Lannea acida</i>	Anemia	Bark	Decoction	I, II, III, IV, V	1	0.071	0.003	Kèlo/Te	NE
<i>Lannea barteri</i>	Anemia / fracture / wounds	Bark	Decoction / maceration / infusion	II, III, IV, V	25	0.214	0.075	Kisan/Ka	NE
<i>Lannea kerstingii</i>	Anemia	Bark	Decoction / infusion	I, II, IV, V	23	0.071	0.069		NE
<i>Launaea taraxacifolia</i>	Teething / intestinal wounds / anemia / blood pressure / vision problems	Leaves / whole plant	Decoction	I, V	31	0.429	0.093	Anonto/Ew	NE
<i>Leptadenia hastata</i>	Cough / ulcer	Whole plant / root	Decoction / infusion	I, II, III, V	26	0.143	0.078	Sopotoriyi/Peu	NE
<i>Lippia multiflora</i>	Anemia	Bark	Decoction	II, IV	2	0.071	0.006	Avudatsi/Ew	NE
<i>Lonchocarpus sericeus</i>	Headache / malaria	Leaves	Decoction / maceration / trituration	II, III, IV, V	8	0.143	0.024	Lonba/Ad	NE
<i>Mallotus oppositifolius</i>	Headache	Leaves	Decoction / maceration	I, II, III, IV, V	4	0.071	0.012	Nyativi/Ew	LC
<i>Markhamia lutea</i>	Scabies	Leaves	Decoction / maceration	II	8	0.071	0.024		LC
<i>Mezoneuron benthamianum</i>	Antiseptic / sexual dysfunction	Leaves / stem	Maceration	III, IV, V	11	0.143	0.033	Gbigbova/Ew	NE
<i>Milicia excelsa</i>	Madness / edema / malaria / female sterility	Bark / leaves	Decoction	II, IV, V	28	0.286	0.084	Odoum/Akp	NT
<i>Monodora myristica</i>	Sores / sexual dysfunction / stomach ache	Fruit	Trituration	II, IV, V	10	0.143	0.03	Asioti/Mi	LC
<i>Morinda lucida</i>	Fever / hypertension / icterus / stomach ache / malaria / taenia	Leaves / root	Decoction / maceration	I, III, IV, V	46	0.357	0.137	Dadaklalan/Ew	LC
<i>Newbouldia laevis</i>	Malaria / wounds	Leaves	Decoction / maceration / trituration	II, IV, V	27	0.214	0.081	Kpatima/Ew	NE
<i>Ocimum americanum</i>	Fever / headache / malaria / felon	Leaves / stem	Decoction / infusion / maceration	I, II, III, IV, V	31	0.214	0.093	Defetsui/Ew	NE
<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>	Stomach ache	Leaves	Decoction / maceration / trituration	I, II, III, IV, V	9	0.071	0.027	Esrou/Ew	NE
<i>Ocimum canum</i>	Stomach ache / wound	Leaves	Decoction / maceration	I, II, III, IV, V	4	0.071	0.012	Aswoeloo/Ka	LC
<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>	Constipation / diarrhea / stomach ache / sores	Leaves	Decoction / maceration	IV, V	27	0.214	0.081	Hetchagni/Ag	NE
<i>Opilia amentacea</i>	Malaria / fatigue	Leaves	Crush	I, II, III, V	8	0.071	0.024	Kalibinou/Ka	NE
<i>Parinari excelsa</i>	Diarrhea	Stem	Decoction / maceration	IV	9	0.071	0.027	Kura/Peu	LC
<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	Abdominal wounds / malaria	Bark	Decoction / trituration	I, II, III, IV, V	17	0.071	0.051	Wotsi/Ew	NE
<i>Passiflora foetida</i>	Anemia / malaria	Leaves	Decoction	I, IV, V	30	0.214	0.09	Gbanto gbantwe/Adj	NE
<i>Pergularia daemia</i>	Vertigo	Leaves	Decoction	I, II, IV, V	1	0.071	0.003	Halbodo/Ka	LC
<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Hip and stomach pain / malaria	Leaves / fruit / whole plant / root	Decoction	I, II, III, V	38	0.286	0.113	Hlinvi/Ew	NE
<i>Piliostigma thonningii</i>	Bleeding / stomach ache / malaria / body wounds	Leaves / whole plant	Maceration	I, II, III, IV, V	19	0.286	0.057	Boboou/Ka	NE

Table 3: Continued

TMP/Family	Medicinal use TMP	Plant parts	Preparation method	Ecological zone	UR	Ivi	CI	Local name	Statut IUCN
<i>Piper guineense</i>	Stomach ache / abdominal wounds	Fruit / root	Decoction / maceration	IV	17	0.143	0.051	Kouleboe/Aké	LC
<i>Piper nigrum</i>	Wounds / sexual dysfunction	Fruit / root	Decoction / maceration	IV	4	0.071	0.012	Akposso/Adj	
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	Dermatosis / snake-bite	Leaves / stem	Decoction / crush and put in sauce	I, II, IV, V	9	0.143	0.027	Ebouatcho/Akp	LC
<i>Prosopis africana</i>	Cavity / dermatosis / hemorrhoids	Bark / leaves	Decoction	I, II, III	16	0.214	0.048	Balo/Ka	LC
<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Diarrhea / laxative	Root / stem	Decoction / maceration	I, II, III, IV, V	21	0.071	0.063	Alelo/La	NE
<i>Pteleopsis suberosa</i>	Intestinal and skin wounds	Leaves	Decoction	II	3	0.071	0.009	Kizisina/Ka	LC
<i>Pterocarpus erinaceus</i>	Dysentery / sexual dysfunction / deworming	Bark / leaves / root	Decoction / maceration	I, II, III	21	0.143	0.063	Ntem/Ka	EN
<i>Pterocarpus santalinoides</i>	Dysentery	Leaves	Decoction	III, V	3	0.071	0.009	Kpesna/Mb	LC
<i>Pupalia lappacea</i>	Wounds	Leaves	Decoction	III, V	4	0.071	0.012	Tetemalima/Ew	LC
<i>Raphia vinifera</i>	Wounds	Leaves	Decoction	III, V	4	0.071	0.012	Alati/Ew	LC
<i>Rauvolfia vomitoria</i>	Aphrodisiac / hemorrhoids / malaria	Leaves / root	Decoction	III, IV, V	13	0.214	0.039	Dodema-kpowoè/Ew	LC
<i>Sarcocephalus latifolius</i>	Malaria / stomach ache / abdominal and intestinal wounds	Bark / leaves / root	Decoction	I, II, III, IV, V	104	0.357	0.31	Nyimon/Ew	LC
<i>Securidaca longipedunculata</i>	Snakebite / sinusitis / head wounds	Leaves / root	Decoction	I, II, III, IV, V	34	0.143	0.101	Tritou/Ew	NE
<i>Securinega virosa</i>	Malaria / head and stomach aches	Leaves / whole plant / root	Decoction	III, V	68	0.357	0.203	Hesre/Ew	LC
<i>Sida acuta</i>	Complication of childbirth	Leaves	Decoction	I, II, III, V	20	0.071	0.06	Afidémè/Adj	NE
<i>Spathodea campanulata</i>	Wounds / infertility / anemia / malaria	Bark	Chew / cataplasm / maceration / powder	III, IV, V	20	0.143	0.06	Adatsigolo/Ew	LC
<i>Spondias mombin</i>	Candidiasis/ leprosy / postpartum bleeding	Leaves / root	Decoction	I, II, III, IV, V	22	0.286	0.066	Akikonti/Ew	LC
<i>Strophanthus hispidus</i>	Malaria / skin wounds	Leaves	Maceration	I, III, IV, V	16	0.143	0.048	Pitombayi/Ew	LC
<i>Tapinanthus bangwensis</i>	Cough	Leaves / root	Decoction	II, III, IV, V	12	0.143	0.036	Gui/Ew	NE
<i>Terminalia superba</i>	Anemia / vomiting	Bark	Maceration	IV	2	0.071	0.006	Donko/Ew	NE
<i>Tetrapleura tetraptera</i>	Abscess / gonorrhoea	Leaves / root	Decoction / maceration	III, IV	15	0.286	0.045	Ledza/Ew	LC
<i>Thevetia peruviana</i>	Abscess / gonorrhoea / ulcer	Leaves / root / sap	Infusion / decoction	I, II, III, IV, V	12	0.214	0.036	Thevetia/Ew	LC
<i>Triplochiton scleroxylon</i>	Wounds	Bark	Decoction	III, IV	9	0.071	0.027	Atiyhe/Ew	LC
<i>Uvaria chamae</i>	Anemia / wounds / female sterility / cough	Leaves / root	Decoction / maceration	II, III, V	52	0.286	0.155	Agbana/Ew	LC
<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i>	Stomach ache/malaria /abdominal sores	Leaves	Decoction	I, IV, V	8	0.214	0.024	Aloma/Ew	NE
<i>Vernonia cinerea</i>	Fever / toothache / female sterility	Leaves / stem	Trituration	I, II, IV, V	12	0.143	0.036	Hunsikonou/Adj	NE
<i>Vitellaria paradoxa</i>	Icterus / sexual dysfunction / head ache / sores / colds	Almond/ bark/leaves / latex	Decoction / trituration	I, II, III, IV, V	29	0.286	0.087	Yokuti/Ew	VU
<i>Vitex doniana</i>	Diuretic/ frigidity/ icterus/body wounds/ liver problems/ strengthens teeth	Bark / leaves / root	Food / decoction / trituration	I, II, III, IV, V	27	0.357	0.081	Otitikpe/Aké	NE

Table 3: Continued

TMP/Family	Medicinal use TMP	Plant parts	Preparation method	Ecological zone	UR	Ivi	CI	Local name	Statut IUCN
<i>Ximenia americana</i>	Diarrhea / eczema	Leaves	Decoction	I, V	19	0.143	0.057	Roumouloung/Na	LC
<i>Xylopia aethiopica</i>	Dysmenorrhea / fever / malaria / sexual dysfunction	Leaves / fruit / root / stem	Decoction / maceration / trituration	I, II, III, IV, V	41	0.286	0.122	Etso/Ew	LC
<i>Zanthoxylum leprieurii</i>	Abdominal wounds	Bark	Decoction / maceration	IV	5	0.071	0.015	Xéti/Ew	NE
<i>Zanthoxylum macrophylla</i>	Stomach ache / abdominal pain / malaria	Bark	Decoction / trituration	IV	16	0.286	0.048	Xéti/Ew	NE
<i>Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides</i>	Aphrodisiac / post-delivery wounds / internal wounds for nursing mothers / malaria	Bark / leaves / whole plant / root	Decoction / dry and crush	I, III, V	74	0.5	0.221	Xéti/Ew	LC

Ad: Adja; Ag: Agnanga; Aké: Akébou; Akp: Akposso; Ew: Ewé; Ka: Kabyè; La: Lamba; Mb: Moba; Mi: Mina; Na: Nawdba; Peu: Peulh and Te: Tem

Plant parts and medicinal recipe preparation methods

The interviewees use different plant parts, alone or in combination, for the preparation of medicinal recipes. In this study, eleven (11) plant parts were identified (Figure 2): leaves (64.8%) remained the most commonly used, followed by roots (37.5%), bark (22.7%), and stem (14.8%). These results are similar to those obtained by Ouattara (2006) in Côte d'Ivoire and Olivier *et al.* (2012) in Burkina Faso.

Leaves are the most used for the preparation of medicinal recipes, as they are more accessible (Mounkaila *et al.*, 2017) and are a safe identification factor for users (Asase *et al.*, 2005). Also, leaves, thanks to the photosynthesis phenomenon, remain the primary production site of secondary metabolites. Depending on the nature of the disease, a specific mode of extraction is used. The surveys identified seven (07) methods of preparing medicinal recipes (Figure 3). Of these, the three most commonly used methods of preparation were decoction (76.6%), maceration (35.2%), and roasting (17.2%). These results are similar to those found by Gnagne *et al.* (2017) in Côte d'Ivoire. Indeed, these different techniques of extraction of active principles from plant organs explain the use of a plant in the treatment of several pathologies or

Figure 2: Plant part frequency

Figure 3: Frequency of use and preparation of drug recipes

Table 4: IFC by disease category

Disease category	Number of plant	Nur	IFC
A General and Unspecified disease	45	346	0.87
B Blood, Blood Forming Organs and Immune Mechanism disease	58	554	0.90
D Digestive	33	320	0.90
K Cardiovascular	8	49	0.85
L Osteoarticular	21	245	0.92
N Musculoskeletal	5	29	0.86
P Psychological	2	9	0.88
R Respiratory	16	112	0.86
S Skin	62	473	0.87
T Endocrine/Metabolic and Nutritional	2	11	0.90
W Pregnancy, Childbearing, Family Planning	8	61	0.88
X Female Genital	15	111	0.87
Y Male Genital	17	76	0.79

symptoms (N'guessan *et al.*, 2009). Decoction remains the most used extraction method in the world because it allows, on the one hand, complete extraction of active principles (especially tannins) from the plant organs (Etame-Loe *et al.*, 2018), and on the other hand, because it mitigates or cancels the toxic effect of some medicinal recipes (Salhi *et al.*, 2019; Koman *et al.*, 2021). However, it should be noted that respondents have difficulties in putting differences between “decoction” and “infusion”.

Informant Consensus Factor

The high consensus factor index (above 0.79) demonstrates strong agreement on the TMP used in each category of disease (Table 4). These results are similar to those obtained by Gumisiriza *et al.* (2019) and Anywar *et al.*, (2020) in Uganda. This index reflects good knowledge of PMTs due to cultural mixing during inter-ethnic marriages (Atakpama *et al.*, 2015) or fine environmental control. Skin diseases (S), those related to the immunological system (B), and those of a general and non-specific nature (A) are treated, respectively, by 62, 58, and 45 TMP. However, dermatitis, wounds, and malaria constitute important scourges in rural environments. The scarcity of these TMP makes it difficult to find a cure for these diseases, especially in poor families.

CONCLUSION

In the Guinean zone of Togo, there is a rich diversity (124) of medicinal plants that are threatened with extinction. This phytodiversity is essential for the local populations because they are used in the treatment of general and non-specific ailments, with general illnesses taking the lead. The plant parts and mode of preparation most used were leaves (64.8%) and decoction (76.6%), respectively. The pharmacological tests confirm the validity of medicinal recipes based on these TMP. This list remains threatened due to the increasing pressure on the collection of plant parts. However, a judicious use of herbal remedies is necessary to prevent resistance and public health issues. It is essential to promote domestication efforts to carry out their conservation.

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